

Quantifying cell cycle dependent chromatin dynamics during interphase by live 3D tracking

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Summary

The study of cell cycle progression and regulation is important to our understanding of fundamental biophysics, aging, and disease mechanisms. Local chromatin movements are generally considered to be constrained and relatively consistent during all interphase stages, although recent advances in our understanding of genome organization challenge this claim. Here we use high spatio-temporal, 4D (x, y, z + time) localization microscopy by point spread function (PSF) engineering and deep learning-based image analysis, for live imaging of mouse embryonic fibroblast (MEF 3T3) and MEF 3T3 double Lamin A Knockout (LmnaKO) cell lines, to characterize telomere diffusion during the interphase. We detected varying constraint levels imposed on the chromatin, which are prominently decreased during G0/G1. Our 4D measurements of telomere diffusion offer an effective method to investigate chromatin dynamics and reveal cell-cycle-dependent motion constraints, which may be caused by various cellular processes.

Keywords

Cell cycle, MEF 3T3, 3D genome organization, chromatin dynamics, chromatin regulation, Lamin A, genome structure and function, live-cell imaging, single-particle tracking, super-resolution microscopy, localization microscopy, point spread function (PSF) engineering, artificial intelligence (AI), deep learning, convolutional neural network (CNN), MSD analysis.

Introduction

There has been a growing interest in 3D genome organization and dynamics in recent years (Maeshima *et al.*, 2020). The basic structure, namely the 10 nm chromatin fiber, is composed of DNA wrapped on a histone core to form nucleosomes, separated by non-nucleosome linker DNA and other DNA binding proteins. The current model for genome organization has been enhanced using different methods, including cryo-EM tomography (Eltsov *et al.*, 2008; Cai *et al.*, 2018), X-ray scattering (Nishino *et al.*, 2012), super-resolution microscopy (STORM and PALM) (Ricci *et al.*, 2015; Nozaki *et al.*, 2017), and genomic methods (Lieberman-Aiden and Berkum, 2009; Hsieh *et al.*, 2015; Sanborn *et al.*, 2015; Ohno *et al.*, 2019). The clustering of nucleosomes to form domains (Sanborn *et al.*, 2015; Nozaki *et al.*, 2017), which vary in size and shape (Ricci *et al.*, 2015; Maeshima *et al.*, 2020; Lin *et al.*, 2021), is a dynamic process (Bintu *et al.*, 2018). The biophysical properties of the domains were extensively investigated, and include condensate-formation, possibly by liquid-liquid phase separation (Banani *et al.*, 2017; Strom *et al.*, 2017; Gibson *et al.*, 2019; Sanulli *et al.*, 2019; Lee *et al.*, 2020), leading to local isolated environments. The clustering of several domains into transcriptionally-active compartments (euchromatin) and generally-silent compartments (heterochromatin) (Lieberman-Aiden and Berkum, 2009) make up the chromosome that occupies a distinct volume in the nucleus, namely a chromosome territory (Maeshima *et al.*, 2020).

Live-cell imaging and optical-field-correlation maps have revealed dynamic structural changes in Chromatin (Nozaki *et al.*, 2017; Bintu *et al.*, 2018; Shaban *et al.*, 2020). Local chromatin (single domain) motion is generally constrained (subdiffusive), however, it can also exhibit Brownian-like (free) and active transport (superdiffusive) behaviors (Chuang *et al.*, 2006; Bronshtein *et al.*, 2015a; Nozaki *et al.*, 2017; Shaban *et al.*, 2020), [Figure 1B](#). The constrained dynamics of chromatin is explained by the necessity to preserve nucleus compartmentalization, which is maintained by the activity of several factors, such as cohesin (Liu *et al.*, 2021), condensin, and lamins (Bronshtein *et al.*, 2015a; Narendra *et al.*, 2015; Vivante *et al.*, 2019; Karoutas and Akhtar, 2021), in particular nucleoplasm Lamin A. On the other hand, rapid turnovers of domain formation and disassembly (Bintu *et al.*, 2018), as well as repositioning events (Levi *et al.*, 2005; Albiez *et al.*, 2006; Chowdhary *et al.*, 2019; Fasciani *et al.*, 2020) and transient compartment formation (Cisse *et al.*, 2013; Furlong and Levine, 2018; Fasciani *et al.*, 2020; Kim and Kingston, 2020), for example for transcription activation, and preparation for division, can contribute to more freely-diffusing motion.

The cell cycle is a well-regulated process that includes distinct phases: during gap phase 1 (G1) the cell increases in size, and then enters the synthesis phase (S) in which the genetic material is being replicated, followed by further cell expansion in gap phase 2 (G2), leading to the mitotic phase (M) where the cell divides (Humphrey and Brooks, 2005). Cell population in G1 may enter the resting phase (G0) (Da Silva-álvarez and Collado, 2018); when this phase is reversible, it is referred to as quiescent G0. For populations

that include both G1 and quiescent G0 cells, the first phase of the interphase is referred to as G0/G1 (Hahn, Jones and Meyer, 2009). While cell-cycle dependant epigenetic mechanisms (Bui *et al.*, 2012), such as protein-chromatin interactions, are well known, fundamental questions regarding chromosome dynamics during the interphase remain open. The leading opinion was that local chromatin motion is similar throughout the different phases (G1/G0, S, and G2) (Nozaki *et al.*, 2017). However, recent studies suggest differently: all-nucleus scale analysis reported different chromatin dynamics between G0 and G1 cells (Shaban *et al.*, 2020), and single-locus analysis in U2OS show that domains possibly undergo condensation-relaxation cycles during the transition from G1 to S and from S to G2 (Ma *et al.*, 2019).

Fluorescence microscopy is used to directly observe chromatin in live cells (Weiss, Naor and Shechtman, 2018). However, conventional volumetric (3D) imaging is based on scanning (confocal or Z stack), which limits the temporal and spatial resolutions of the microscope. Point-Spread-Function (PSF) engineering enables 3D imaging without scanning, achieving high framerates. This is done by inserting a specially designed optical element, namely a phase mask, into the microscope. Emitted light from the sample is modulated by the phase mask such that its 3D information is encoded in the 2D image that a point emitter generates on the camera (the PSF). Then, using image analysis (Pavani *et al.*, 2009; Backer and Moerner, 2014; Shechtman *et al.*, 2015, 2017; Von Diezmann, Shechtman and Moerner, 2017), a precise 3D estimate of the emitter's position, i.e. a localization, is obtained (Figure 1A). This spatial encoding makes high densities of fluorescent molecules, where there is significant spatial overlap of PSFs, a challenging image processing problem of multi-emitter localization. Recently, our group introduced a deep learning-based method (DeepStorm3D (Nehme *et al.*, 2020)), which we employ here, to handle dense-emitter samples, such as fluorescently labeled telomeres in the nucleus, enabling high spatiotemporal resolution in >50 positions in a single nucleus simultaneously. The method provides both the optimal phase-mask design and the accompanying image analysis algorithm (Nehme *et al.*, 2020).

Here, we characterize cell-cycle dependent telomere diffusion during the different interphase stages (G0/G1, S, G2, late G2) in live mouse embryonic fibroblast (MEF 3T3) and MEF 3T3 double Lamin A Knockout (LmnaKO) cell lines, using 4D localization microscopy (x, y, z and time) by PSF engineering combined with neural-net based image analysis (Nehme *et al.*, 2020). Since telomeres are spread throughout the nucleus, our simultaneous measurement of multi-telomere diffusion represents local chromatin (single domain) movement across the genome. We report three main results and conclusions based on our observations: (1) The motion constraints normally imposed on chromatin are significantly relaxed during G0/G1 relative to the other stages in the cell cycle; (2) under Lamin A depletion, chromatin motion becomes more Brownian-like, irrespective of cell-cycle phase, such that the observed differences are significantly reduced; (3) the 3D motion of chromatin is anisotropic. This is possibly the result of the inherent anisotropy of adherent cells.

Results and discussion

To compare the motion of chromatin at different stages of the cell cycle, we tracked telomeres, labeled by DsRed-hTRF1 (see STAR methods for details), in 3D with high spatio-temporal resolution (xy : ~ 20 nm; z : ~ 50 nm; t : 10 Hz, see SI: [Table S1](#)). Prior to live cell imaging, MEF 3T3 and MEF LmnaKO cells were synchronized to different phases in the cell cycle. To track the 3D positions at high framerates, we engineered a PSF optimized for a depth range of 2-6 μm above the coverslip, which allows us to image a 4 μm Z section of nucleus without scanning. To extract the 3D trajectories, the raw images underwent a post-processing pipeline which includes frame-by-frame localization using DeepSTORM3D (Ferdman *et al.*, 2020; Nehme *et al.*, 2020), followed by reconstruction of telomere trajectories (telomere 3D positions over time, [Figure 1B](#)) using a custom python code (See SI: [Figure S1](#) for analysis details). To characterize the dynamics of each population (cell cycle phases), we analyzed all the 3D trajectories from all cells for each phase separately, using mean squared displacement (MSD, [Figure 1C](#)), which corresponds to the mean distance that a telomere will travel within a specific time interval (τ), ranging from 100 ms to 30 s.

We quantitatively characterize chromatin motion for each phase using the following set of parameters: anomalous exponent (α), diffusion constant (D_α) and constraining volume (V_c). The anomalous exponent (α) defines the type of motion, as illustrated in [Figure 1C](#), and is calculated for each trajectory from the slope of two linear fits of the MSD curve, corresponding to small intervals ($\tau < \tau_r$) and large intervals ($[\tau_L, 30 \text{ s}]$) ([Figure 2A,C](#)). τ_r and τ_L represent transition times (De Gennes, 1971; Briels, W, 1998; Bronstein *et al.*, 2009), where the ensemble MSD curve change trends from deep subdiffusion to moderate subdiffusion (See STAR methods for precise definition of transition times). The diffusion constant ($D_\alpha \left[\frac{\mu\text{m}^2}{\text{s}^\alpha} \right]$), associated with chromatin condensation (Ma *et al.*, 2019; Shaban *et al.*, 2020), is calculated from the independent variable of the MSD linear fit of the short time intervals, $t < \tau_r$. The constraining volume ($V_c [\mu\text{m}^3]$) is the mean volume that a telomere “explores” within 25 seconds, estimated by calculating the convex hull of each telomere-trajectory (see STAR methods).

Local chromatin 3D motion is less constrained during G0/G1 phase

Our first question is whether local chromatin movements manifest different dynamics during the different stages of the interphase. To do so, MEF 3T3 cells were synchronized in G0/G1, S, early G2, and late G2 phase and were then imaged for 150 s with 100 ms exposure time, using the PSF-engineered microscope (cell cycle stage was verified by flow cytometry, see SI: [Figure S3](#)). Approximately 1300 fluorescently-labeled telomeres were tracked, several hundreds in each phase (see SI: [Table S2](#)). Trajectories were analyzed individually and results were grouped by phase. We determined the level of constraint described by the anomalous exponent and distinguished between short and long time intervals. For the short times ($\tau < \tau_r$) no significant differences were observed between the phases ($\alpha \sim 0.2$, [Figure 2B](#)); while for longer timescales ($t \in [\tau_L, 30 \text{ sec}]$) we identified different constraint levels ([Figure 2A-B](#)): deep subdiffusion during S, $\langle \alpha \rangle = 0.41 \pm 0.29$ and late G2, $\langle \alpha \rangle = 0.47 \pm 0.3$; moderate subdiffusion during early G2, $\langle \alpha \rangle = 0.59 \pm 0.32$; and free subdiffusion, $\langle \alpha \rangle = 0.83 \pm 0.34$ during G0/G1 (mean ± 1 std).

Our findings, which were performed on cells with a normal cell-cycle over the entire nucleus, show that the 3D local chromatin motion varies during the interphase, consistently with a 2D single-chromosome

analysis performed by Ma et al (Ma *et al.*, 2019), which challenged the claim that chromosome motion is consistent during the interphase (Nozaki *et al.*, 2017). Ma et al. tracked two loci on chromosome 19 in cancer cells with an abnormal cell-cycle (U2OS), and showed that their centroid trajectories have a higher anomalous exponent in G1 compared to early S phase. In the current work, our conclusion about local chromatin motion is general: we find that telomere diffusion exhibits significant heterogeneity in terms of the anomalous exponent distribution even in the same cell (Figure 1B) (Bronshtein *et al.*, 2015a; Shaban *et al.*, 2020); yet, overall, telomere diffusion is phase-dependant (Figure 2A-B) in cells with a normal cell cycle.

To summarize, by calculating 3D telomere diffusion we have found that different levels of constraint are imposed on the chromatin in different interphase stages; where the most constrained diffusion is observed during the S and late G2 phases, and the least constraint, i.e. least constrained diffusion dynamics are observed during the G0/G1.

Lamin A depletion decreases constraint differences between cell cycle phases

Lamin A is a protein involved in maintaining the nuclear envelope integrity, protecting the genome from mechanical stress and preserving nuclear compartmentalization (Johnson *et al.*, 2004; Nitta *et al.*, 2006; Scaffidi, 2006; Nitta, Smith and Kennedy, 2007; Bronshtein *et al.*, 2015a; Shachar *et al.*, 2015; Karoutas and Akhtar, 2021). In addition, a mutant cell line with double knock-out of Lamin A, *MEF LmnaKO* cells, exhibits defective cell cycle regulation (Johnson *et al.*, 2004; Nitta *et al.*, 2006; Dechat *et al.*, 2007; Nitta, Smith and Kennedy, 2007; Cho *et al.*, 2019), as also indicated by our flow cytometry results (Figure S3). Furthermore, *MEF LmnaKO* cells are an important model for premature aging studies (Oshima *et al.*, 2007; Ghosh and Zhou, 2014; Grigoryan *et al.*, 2018). In light of the cell-cycle dependant chromatin motion we observed in *MEF 3T3* cells we raised a question: Is it possible that the function of Lamin A has an effect on chromatin motion patterns during the interphase?

To examine this possibility, we performed 3D telomere tracking in a mutant cell line with double knock-out of Lamin A, *MEF LmnaKO*, and compared the results to the normal cell line (*MEF 3T3*). Interestingly, the differences in anomalous diffusion coefficients between the cell-cycle phases in the mutant cells were significantly decreased compared to the normal cells; free subdiffusion was detected in all phases, reaching values close to pure Brownian motion ($\langle\alpha\rangle \approx 1$) in G0/G1 (Figure 2C-D). This observation is consistent with an earlier study reporting telomere free subdiffusion in *MEF LmnaKO* without synchronization for cell cycle phases (Bronshtein *et al.*, 2015a).

Axial and lateral diffusions during the interphase are different

Adherent cells have anisotropic dimensions, namely, stretching much further laterally (xy) than normal to the surface (z). It is therefore not surprising that this inherent anisotropy yields a difference in motion between the lateral and the axial dimensions, which is directly observable by our live 3D imaging method. To explore the contributions of the lateral and axial motions to telomere dynamic constraint, we re-ran the ensemble MSD analysis for the lateral and Axial coordinates separately (Figure 3 and Figure S2), comparing the constraint levels using the anomalous exponent (α). Overall, throughout interphase, lateral motion appeared less confined than axial motion (Figure 3). With respect to the different cell-cycle stages, in both the lateral and axial analyses, G0/G1 presented more free diffusion than other phases. The anomalous exponent of the lateral analysis identified that G0/G1 and G2 had higher values than S and late G2, while G0/G1 presented a higher value compared with G2. Interestingly, the axial analysis presented a different situation: Late G2 presented a higher value than S and G2, in which the axial chromosome movement was extremely constrained (Figure 3A).

A reasonable explanation for the different constraints between phases is DNA content and chromatin density: increased DNA content should increase the density and decrease the diffusion constant D_α , which is traditionally associated with chromatin condensation (Ma *et al.*, 2019; Shaban *et al.*, 2020). $D_\alpha \left[\frac{\mu m^2}{s^\alpha} \right]$ is dependant on α , and therefore constitutes a good metric for comparison when the different populations have similar mean α . Accordingly, we calculated the diffusion constant from the short interval times linear fit ($\tau < \tau_r$), where the values of α are similar for all the phases, and identified slightly higher value during G0/G1 (Figure 4A), in agreement with the lower expected DNA content levels during G0/G1. We did not calculate D_α for the long interval times ($\tau > \tau_L$), because the α values vary between the phases. Instead, we compared the constraining volumes (V_c), namely the volumes explored by the telomeres within 25 s, for the 3D trajectories (Figure 4C), using convex hull analysis (Figure 4B, see STAR methods for more details). This analysis revealed a similar picture to the one provided by D_α for the short time intervals (Figure 4A).

In the axial motion, for both the wild-type and lamin A KO cells, the constraint increased from G0/G1 to the S phase and was maximal in early G2 (Figure 3A). This possibly implies an effect of the amount of DNA on chromatin motion: DNA is doubled during the S phase, while the overall size of the nucleus during all interphase remains relatively constant (Walter *et al.*, 2003); hence, diffusion is expected to be more constrained. The less constrained axial motion during the late G2 phase compared with S and early G2 may derive from the condensation of the chromosome as preparation for mitosis, which reaches a maximum during metaphase anaphase transition (mitosis was not investigated in this research).

The change in DNA content is not sufficient to explain the cell-cycle-dependent local chromatin motion, as evident in the WT lateral diffusion results, showing relaxation during early G2 compared to the S phase (Figure 3A). A possible explanation for this effect may be chromosome compartmentalization; the dynamic segregation (Bintu *et al.*, 2018) of the chromosome into local domains of different sizes may vary during the interphase as part of the phase-dependant cell processes. During S phase, the replication of the genome occurs in multiple loci simultaneously, and the chromosome may segregate into smaller

domains (Nozaki *et al.*, 2017; Bintu *et al.*, 2018; Ashwin *et al.*, 2019). Our observation of similar constraints during the S and G2 phases in LmnaKO cells (Figure 2D) supports this explanation; nucleoplasm Lamin A is known to be involved in constraining chromatin dynamics and maintaining nucleus compartmentalization, and therefore its absence will affect the process of chromatin segregation to domains (Bronshtein *et al.*, 2015a; Nozaki *et al.*, 2017; Karoutas and Akhtar, 2021). To summarize this section, our data generally shows that axial and lateral diffusions are different. A reasonable explanation is embedded in cell morphology: in adherent cells, the available space for diffusion is more limited in the axial direction as manifested in generally reduced axial motion in all phases for both cell lines (Figure 3A-B).

Ultimately, chromosomal motion dynamics should be interpreted in the context of the cell's behavior. During G0/G1 a cell's resources are mainly invested in growth, maintenance, and performing the various cell-type-dependent cellular function (e.g. fibroblast, epithelium etc.). Most of the transcription occurs during G1 (Humphrey and Brooks, 2005); accordingly, domain repositioning rates are more frequent, and the chromatin motion is less constrained than other phases. During S phase, chromosomal segregation into more compact domains occurs, which is important for replication of the genome (Nagano *et al.*, 2017; Nozaki *et al.*, 2017; Bintu *et al.*, 2018; Ashwin *et al.*, 2019), and therefore the DNA is most constricted. During G2, the cell prepares for mitosis, including transcription of necessary genes and DNA damage repair. That manifests in a slight relaxation in the constraints, however, DNA content is larger than in the G1 phase, thus limiting the available space for diffusion. In late G2, just before the cell enters prophase (mitosis), the chromosome undergoes significant condensation. The local organization (segregation to domains) is preserved during mitosis (Nozaki *et al.*, 2017), and therefore during late G2, more constrained lateral diffusion may reflect proper condensation and segregation during mitosis.

Closing remarks

In the last decade, our understanding of genome organization and compartmentalization has changed dramatically (Maeshima *et al.*, 2020). Chromatin organization has been found to be highly dynamic at multiple scales, with transient domains forming frequently (Bintu *et al.*, 2018). This local reordering is reflected in the large heterogeneity of local chromatin motion. Our results demonstrate that local chromatin constraints are phase dependant. Furthermore, our unique method revealed different behavior of axial and lateral diffusion in adherent cells, which motivates future investigation into the 3D organization of the nucleus, in the context of 3D culture and in vivo studies. Under Lamin A depletion the differences between the cell cycle phases were decreased, consistent with Lamin A's function in the preservation of the constrained chromatin diffusion and stability of chromosome segregation to domains. This adds to the growing body of evidence (Johnson *et al.*, 2004; Nitta *et al.*, 2006; Nitta, Smith and Kennedy, 2007; Hara *et al.*, 2012; Bronshtein *et al.*, 2015b; Vivante *et al.*, 2019; Karoutas and Akhtar, 2021) that ties the involvement of Lamin A to premature aging diseases and other diseases involved with major genome organization instability and cell cycle dysregulation.

Limitations of Study

We used a motif binding protein, hTRF1, fused to a FP - DsRed. This chimeric protein, DsRed-hTRF1, specifically binds the repeated sequences in the telomere, such that an array of FPs is formed on telomere sites, allowing to track telomeres as single particles. Generally, when using single-particle tracking (SPT) methods, due to high NA, one should consider the strong polarization along the illumination direction. However, in our work, the signal from each telomere originates from a multitude of fluorescent proteins at random orientations aggregated together at high rotational mobility, several microns above the coverslip. Under these circumstances, we do not observe that the polarization of the illumination has a noticeable effect. As mentioned in the text, we did not separate the quiescent population from the G1 cells; one can design an experiment using other synchronization reagents to separate these populations as well. Finally, the more data the better – the more cells, telomeres, and conditions that can be measured, the more the statistical significance of our findings would improve.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization- TN; Methodology -sample preparation- TN; Methodology – optical setup- BF and LEW; Methodology – Localization- TN, EN, BF; Methodology – trajectory extraction- YN; Methodology – Data analysis- TN; Software- EN, BF, YN, and TN; Writing- TN, OA, and YS; Supervision- OA and YS;

Declaration of interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Main figure titles and captions

Figure 1: 3D telomere tracking in live cells using PSF engineering. (A) Example image of a live cell containing 3D information of labeled telomere positions using a depth-encoding phase mask in the microscope setup (right), more details in SI: [Figure S1](#). The 3D position of each telomere is determined algorithmically according to an experimentally-derived PSF model obtained from a calibration image-stack of a defocused fluorescent bead (left, distance from the focal plane stated, scale bar = 3 μm). (B) The trajectories of the telomeres are reconstructed from their localization over time (example of four telomeres shown in the bottom) and located in the nucleus. Color indicates time (See [Movie 1](#)). (C) Mean squared displacement (MSD) analysis and the derived anomalous exponent (α) distinguishes between three main types of motion: sub-diffusion, normal diffusion, and super-diffusion. (D) anomalous exponent histogram of all detected telomeres (N=38) in the cell shown in B.

Figure 2: Telomere diffusion analysis in different cell cycle phases. Ensemble mean square displacement (MSD) curves and Anomalous exponent (α) in MEF 3T3 (A, B) and in MEF LmnaKO (C, D) cells. α is represented as violin plots for short interval times ($t < \tau_t$) and long interval times ($t > \tau_t$). Shaded regions in (A, C) mark the short and long interval ranges analyzed for G0/G1. See all transition times values in SI: [Table S2](#). UT – untreated cells. N is number of trajectories analyzed in MEF 3T3. Confidence in two sample tests (See STAR methods for details, and also Table S3): * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure 3: Axial vs lateral analysis and comparison between MEF 3T3 and LmnaKO. (A-B) Anomalous exponent (α) violin plots for the longer time-intervals in MEF 3T3 (A) and LmnaKO (B). The MSD curves were calculated for three cases: Lateral (2D, x, y), axial (z), and 3D (x, y, z). Confidence in two sample tests (See STAR methods for details, and also Table S3): * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure 4: DNA content analysis. (A) diffusion constant D_α for short times ($t < \tau_t$) in MEF 3T3, where α is approximately equal in all phases. (B) An example of constraining volume calculated by convex hull. 2D Projections shown on the XY, XZ, YZ planes. The trajectory is color-coded, and the convex hull volume/area is in gray. (C) constraining volume distribution, calculated by convex hull at time 25 s (see also other times in [Figure S4](#)), for MEF 3T3 (left) and MEF LmnaKO (right). Confidence in two sample tests (See STAR methods for details): + $p < 0.2$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

STAR methods text

RESOURCE AVAILABILITY

Lead contact

Further information and requests should be directed to and will be fulfilled by the lead contact, Yoav Shechtman (yoavsh@technion.ac.il)

Materials availability

This study did not generate new unique reagents.

Data and code availability

- Raw imaging data, and localization results csv files are available from the lead contact upon request.
- Original codes are available for download with the link provided in the KRT section.
- Any additional information required to reanalyze the data reported in this paper is available from the lead contact upon request.

EXPERIMENTAL MODEL AND SUBJECT DETAILS

Mouse embryonic fibroblast (MEF 3T3) and MEF 3T3 double Lamin-A KO cell lines were kindly given by professor Yoav Garini lab. Both cell lines were tested to be mycoplasma-free, using the MycoBlue mycoplasma detector (Vazyme biotech, D101).

METHOD DETAILS

Experimental procedures

Calibration bead sample for phase retrieval

1 % Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) solution was made by dissolving 1 gr PVA powder (Sigma-Aldrich, 341584) in 100ml double distilled water, and mild heating for 24 hr. 0.04 μm FluoSphere 605 nm stock solution (Thermo-fisher, F10720) was diluted 10^{-6} in 1 % PVA. 10 μl of the diluted solution was spread on a glass-bottom culture plate (NEST scientific, 801002) homogenously, using a homemade spin-coater, and dried in a chemical hood.

Live cell sample preparation

MEF 3T3 and MEF 3T3 LmnaKO cells (gift from Y. Garini's lab) were grown for two weeks (four passages) in complete medium containing DMEM-Ham's/F12 (Biological industries, 01-170-1A), supplemented with 10% FBS (Biological industries, 04-007-1A), 1% L-glutamine solution (Biological industries, 03-020-1B) and 1% Penicillin-Streptomycin Solution (Biological industries, 03-031-1B) to allow stable cell cycle. Both cell lines were tested to be mycoplasma-free, using the MycoBlue mycoplasma detector (Vazyme biotech, D101). For each imaging session, two samples were prepared: one for imaging and one for flow cytometry analysis. For imaging samples only, cells were transfected using lipofectamine 3000 (Thermo-fisher,

L3000008): 10 µg DsRed-hTRF1 plasmid (gift from Y. Garini lab) was mixed with 20 µl P3000 reagent in 1 mL phenol red-free DMEM-Ham's/F12 (Gibco, Thermo-fisher, 11039021); 30 µl Lipofectamine3000 was diluted in 1mL phenol red-free DMEM-Ham's/F12; the DNA mix was added to the Lipofectamine 3000 mix and incubated for 30 min in RT. Cell suspension was adjusted to 7.5×10^5 cells/ml and mixed with the transfection mix to a final volume of 10 ml. The cells were then plated in a 75 cm² flask and returned to the incubator for 28 hr before starting synchronization protocols as described below. The control sample for flow cytometry then underwent the same treatments as the imaging sample, except transfection.

Cell cycle phase synchronization

Cells were harvested using Trypsin-EDTA Solution (Biological industries, 03-050-1A), and cell concentration was adjusted to 2×10^6 cells/ml to encourage contact inhibition induced quiescence, due to high cell density. Cells were washed twice (centrifuge at 2200 rpm for 2min) with phosphate buffer saline, PBS (Sigma-Aldrich, 59331C), resuspended in low serum (0.5%) DMEM-Ham's/F12, plated in a 75 cm² flask, and grown for 48 hr. After 48 hr of growth in a low serum medium, each cell sample was treated differently, according to the specific cell cycle phase synchronization protocol: G0/G1 synchronized cells were left to grow an additional 24 hr in a low serum medium; G2 synchronized cells were harvested, concentrated to 7.5×10^5 cells/ml, and re-suspended in a complete medium containing 0.5 µg/ml nocodazole (Acros organics, 358240100), and grown for 48 hr; Late G2 synchronized cells were harvested, concentrated to 7.5×10^5 cells/ml, and re-suspended in a complete medium containing 0.04 µg/ml Colcemid (Sigma-Aldrich, D1925), and grown for 48hr (note that colcemid induces M checkpoint activation, however, hTRF1 binds less efficiently to telomeres during the M phase, thus cells were considered to be in late G2 rather than M phase). 24hr before imaging and while synchronizing; cells were plated on glass-bottom culture plates in their synchronization medium. For S enrichment, cells were harvested, washed twice with PBS, concentrated to 2×10^6 cells/ml, re-suspended in a complete medium containing 2 mM thymidine (Acros, 226740050), and grown for 16 hr. Cells were washed twice with PBS, concentration adjusted to 7.5×10^5 cells/ml, and allowed to recover for 6-8 hr in complete medium on glass-bottom plates (imaging sample) or 25 cm² flask (flow cytometry).

Flow cytometry analysis

Flow cytometry analysis was performed to validate cell cycle synchronizations using cyclin level and DNA content stains, according to several modified protocols (Darzynkiewicz *et al.*, 1996; Pagano, 1996; Lanni and Jacks, 1998; Hinz *et al.*, 1999; Humphrey and Brooks, 2005; Peddibhotla *et al.*, 2009; Da Silva-álvarez and Collado, 2018). Cells were fixed with 4 % PFA (Sigma-Aldrich, 158127) solution and stored at 4 °c until the analysis day. On the same day of analysis cells were permeabilized with 1 % Triton X-100 (Sigma-Aldrich, T8787) for 30 min. The cells were washed twice with PBS and incubated with a primary antibody (either 5.95 [µg/ml] Rabbit monoclonal Anti-Cyclin B1, abcam, ab181593; or 9.7 [µg/ml] Rabbit monoclonal IgG Anti- Cyclin D1, abcam, ab16663) for 1 hr in RT. The cells were then incubated for 30 min with x2000 diluted Goat Anti-Rabbit IgG H&L Alexa Fluor® 488 (abcam, ab150081) on ice. Finally, cells were stained with FxCycle™ PI/RNase Staining Solution (Thermo-Fisher scientific, F10797) following manufacturer protocol. Flow cytometry data was collected using a BD LSR-II analyzer operated by FACS-Diva6.1 software, with 488 nm laser, and either 695/40 or 530/30 emission filters for DNA content or Alexa Fluor® 488, respectively. Data were analyzed using FlowJO v10 software.

Microscopy

PSF engineering included 4f optical system with an optimized phase mask in the emission path, encoding information of a 4 μm axial (Z) range into the 2D image, such that no scanning was required: the different point spread function (PSF) shapes are proportional to the axial position of the given telomere (Nehme *et al.*, 2020). A detailed illustration of the 4f system is given in [Figure S1A](#). Cells were imaged using an inverted fluorescence microscope (Nikon Eclipse Ti), with a $\times 100/1.49$ NA oil objective (SR HP Apo TIRF $\times 100/1.49$ NA, Nikon MRD01995). Fluorescent excitation was performed with 561 nm laser (iChrome MLE, Toptica Photonics). The emitted light was filtered with 617/72 bandpass filter (Semrock, FF02-617/73-25) and was extended by 4f setup, which included spatial light modulator, SLM (PLUTO-2.1, Holoeye Photonics AG) for phase mask projection of the optimized phase mask (Nehme *et al.*, 2020), [Figure S1A](#). Images were acquired using a sCMOS camera (PRIME 95B, Teledyne Photometrics, Tucson, Arizona, USA). Before each imaging session the following preparations were made: 1. A day before, the microscope incubator cage (Okolab) was set to 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 5 % CO_2 ; 2. Just before starting live cell imaging, bead calibration sample with water drop for phase retrieval (Ferdman *et al.*, 2020) was imaged with 61 steps of 100nm (Z-stack), 100mW laser power and exposure time of 300 ms. Live-cell samples were imaged with 10mW laser power and exposure time of 100 ms for 150 s. Automated focusing (Perfect Focus) was active during live cell imaging.

Data analysis and post-processing

Localization by PSF engineering and DeepSTORM3D

To obtain an accurate 3D localization by considering the optical system aberrations, the experimental phase mask was calculated using VIPR algorithm (Ferdman *et al.*, 2020), using the calibration bead sample. The resulting phase mask then was used to train the DeepSTORM3D convolutional-neural-network (CNN) with the specific parameters of each session (see parameters in [Table S1](#)). For the live cell data, the emitters in each frame were localized by the trained nets, one cell at each net run ([Figure S1B](#)). The bead signal is brighter and less noisy than telomeres in a live cell. We use the bead measurements only for calibration of our system; specifically, for the VIPR algorithm for learning the experimental phase mask, namely the shape of the PSF. However, for actual training of the net, the expected signal is calculated from randomly selected live cell data, which defines the photon count parameters (k, θ), see [Table S1](#).

Nucleus Lateral drift compensation

Global motion of the entire nucleus was compensated for, effectively canceled, algorithmically, as follows. For each frame in an acquisition sequence, Scale-invariant feature transform (SIFT) features were used to compute the affine 2D transformation homography matrix relative to the first image in the sequence, using the OpenCV library (Bradski, no date; Lowe, 1999). Then, the lateral coordinates of the localizations in each frame were transformed using the computed homography matrices, while the axial coordinates were left intact ([Figure S1C](#)).

Trajectory reconstruction

After nucleus drift compensation transformation, the whole set of 3D localization points in the image sequence was clustered to trajectories with the DBSCAN(Ester *et al.*, 1996) algorithm, and the points in each cluster were filtered for outliers exclusion, using LOF algorithm (Breunig *et al.*, 2000). Both algorithms were taken from the Scikit-learn (Pedregosa *et al.*, 2011) library. Each separate resulting cluster of points was averaged per frame, resulting in separate trajectories, each having one point per image frame. Then, the trajectories were filtered by keeping only those which are: a) longer than 50 frames and; b) having an average gap length between consecutive points smaller than 100 frames (Figure S1D).

Mean squared displacement (MSD) analysis

A common method to determine the type of a single particle motion is the time average mean squared displacement (TA-MSD), where the average squared distance that a diffusing particle will travel within a specific time window is calculated (Bouchaud and Georges, 1990). The calculation of MSD is given by(Kepten, Bronshtein and Garini, 2013; Kepten *et al.*, 2015) Equation 1.

Equation 1: Mean square displacement (MSD). $|\vec{r}| = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}$ is the 3D position vector, τ - is time interval, given by $\tau = n * \delta t$; δt - is exposure time (frame rate), , and N is the total number of time steps.

$$\langle r^2(\tau) \rangle = (N - n)^{-1} \sum_{m=1}^{N-n} [r(m\delta t + \tau) - r(m\delta t)]^2$$

To identify the type of fractional-Brownian-Motion (fBM) of particle population, power law is applied on MSD, given by (Kepten, Bronshtein and Garini, 2013; Kepten *et al.*, 2015) Equation 2.

Equation 2: fBM MSD power law. $\langle r^2(\tau) \rangle$ is the MSD, α is the anomalous exponent, and $D_\alpha \left[\mu m^2 / s^\alpha \right]$ is the anomalous exponent dependant diffusion constant.

$$\langle r^2(\tau) \rangle = D_\alpha \cdot \tau^\alpha$$

Three types of diffusion can be defined by the anomalous exponent (Figure 1C): constrained diffusion (sub-diffusion) when $\alpha < 1$; pure Brownian motion when $\alpha = 1$; and super-diffusion (dragging force is imposed) when $\alpha > 1$. To find the value of the anomalous exponent and diffusion constant, a linear fit was obtained by the log of Equation 2 divided by time, given by Equation 3(Bouchaud and Georges, 1990; Kepten, Bronshtein and Garini, 2013; Kepten *et al.*, 2015). First, the transition times were determined for each phase from the ensemble MSD curve (Figure S1E), and then the parameters (α, D_α) were calculated for each time zone and each trajectory. For ensemble MSD analysis the minimal length of a trajectory was set to 150 time points.

Equation 3: the linear form of fBM MSD equation.

$$\log\left(\frac{\langle r^2(\tau) \rangle}{\tau}\right) = (\alpha - 1) \log(\tau) + \log(D_\alpha)$$

Determining transition times for MSD analysis

Similarly to the analysis done in (Bronstein 2015), we distinguished between two time zones: short-time intervals, $t < \tau_r$, and long-time intervals, $t \in [\tau_L, 30sec]$. We determined the transition times from the ensemble MSD curve of each phase separately, then calculated the anomalous exponent for each time zone and for each trajectory separately. The first transition time (τ_r) was defined as the longest time interval such that the ensemble MSD curve linear fit provided $\alpha < 0.25$ with Pearson correlation higher than 0.9. τ_L was defined by the shortest time interval such that the linear fit of the interval $[\tau_L, 30sec]$ gave a Pearson correlation value higher than 0.9.

Manual validation of each trajectory

We avoided manual analysis as much as possible. However, some trajectories barely passed the automated filtering requirements, for example, by being slightly longer than threshold, containing gaps slightly smaller than threshold or having multiple number of gaps. Therefore, we validated each trajectory manually and excluded only those who clearly cause biased results.

Constraining volume calculation using convex hull

The constraining volume was calculated directly from the trajectory coordinates within 25 s. before calculation of the convex hull, outliers were removed using median filter (outlier is a value that is more than three scaled median absolute deviations, MAD). The resulted distributions are presented in [Figure 4](#), main text.

QUANTIFICATION AND STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Statistical significance test

Two sample t-tests were performed for all distributions; The null hypothesis defined that the two distributions have the same mean, with unknown variance which may be unequal. We did not apply trim or permutations. Since parameters calculated in biological samples may not fit well normal distributions, to further test the statistical significance in this light, we performed a Mann-Whitney non parametric U test and a two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test, and received similar significances (see [Table S3](#)). U test was run using asymptotic method for p-value calculation, when the alternative hypothesis is that the two sample do not have the same distribution. We did not apply continuity correction. KS test was run with the following parameters: The null hypothesis is that the two distributions are identical, under the assumption that the measured values are from continuous distributions. Also for this test we used asymptotic method for p-value calculation. All functions for the statistical tests are from Python SciPy library.

The three tests are mostly consistent (see [Table S3](#)). In the figures, we report the strictest result of all three tests per case. The p-value reports whether the null hypothesis was rejected, marked in the figures as follows: * for $p < 0.05$, ** for $p < 0.01$ and *** for $p < 0.001$. All p-values for the anomalous exponent statistical tests are presented in [Table S3](#). For the diffusion constant and constraining volume ([figures 4 and S4](#)) we also included a confidence threshold of 80% and mark it differently (+ for $p < 0.2$).

Estimating localization precision

We calculated axial and lateral localization precision using three different methods: 1. by DeepSTORM3D module (Nehme *et al.*, 2020), which uses the simulated training set to estimate axial and lateral precision (see [Table S1](#)); 2. using the ensemble MSD curves, of the axial and lateral analysis separately, to estimate localization error as explained in earlier studies (Michalet and Berglund, 2012; Shechtman *et al.*, 2015). The reduced square localization error (ε) is given by Equation 4:

Equation 4: Reduced squared localization error, ε . σ^2 is the squared static localization error, D_α is the diffusion constant, Δt is the exposure time and R is the motion blur coefficient.

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\sigma^2}{D_\alpha \Delta t} - 2R$$

We calculated σ^2 from the first three time points in the MSD curve, by a linear fit, while σ^2 is the intersection of this line with y axis. The diffusion constant (D_α) was calculated from the 3D analysis, the exposure time was 0.1 sec and we ignored motion blur ($R=0$).

3. We used the “slowest” telomeres (with very low anomalous exponent) as an approximation for an *in-cellulo* fiducial, and bound the precision by repeatedly localizing them in 3D for all measured time points (up to 1500 frames), and removing a low-order polynomial (degree 5) for canceling slow motion. The resulted values are presented in [Table S1](#). Note that since these telomeres still exhibit some motion, this quantification could be regarded as a ‘worst-case’ bound on experimental localization precision.

Estimating axial drift compensation

The comparison between the contribution of axial and lateral information ([Figure 3A-B](#)) implied that 2D analysis provides only partial information on the cell-cycle dependency of local chromatin movements on a genome-wide scale. To validate that compensation of axial drift is not required, we examined all cells with at least 10 detected trajectories and calculated the center of mass (CM) for the Z coordinate only. Next, we fitted a 5th degree polynomial to the CM trajectory ([Figure S2B](#)) and subtracted this curve from each trajectory. we find very slight differences between the compensated and not compensated data ([Figure S2C](#)). Accordingly, and to avoid the risk of 'over-correction', the analysis presented in the main text includes all cells and trajectories used for the 3D analysis without compensation for axial drift.

Supplemental item titles

Supplemental item includes a primary supplemental PDF file and one movie.

Supplementary information file. Combined Pdf file includes 4 figures and 3 tables.

Movie 1: trajectory reconstruction animation. related to [Figure 1](#) in the main text.

References

- Albiez, H. *et al.* (2006) 'Chromatin domains and the interchromatin compartment form structurally defined and functionally interacting nuclear networks', *Chromosome Research*, 14(7), pp. 707–733. doi: 10.1007/s10577-006-1086-x.
- Ashwin, S. S. *et al.* (2019) 'Organization of fast and slow chromatin revealed by single-nucleosome dynamics', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 116(40), pp. 19939–19944. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1907342116.
- Backer, A. S. and Moerner, W. E. (2014) 'Extending Single-Molecule Microscopy Using Optical Fourier Processing', *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*. American Chemical Society, 118(28), pp. 8313–8329. doi: 10.1021/jp501778z.
- Banani, S. F. *et al.* (2017) 'Biomolecular condensates: Organizers of cellular biochemistry', *Nature Reviews Molecular Cell Biology*. Nature Publishing Group, 18(5), pp. 285–298. doi: 10.1038/nrm.2017.7.
- Bintu, B. *et al.* (2018) 'Super-resolution chromatin tracing reveals domains and cooperative interactions in single cells', *Science*, 362(6413). doi: 10.1126/science.aau1783.
- Bouchaud, J. P. and Georges, A. (1990) 'Anomalous diffusion in disordered media: Statistical mechanisms, models and physical applications', *Physics Reports*, 195(4–5), pp. 127–293. doi: 10.1016/0370-1573(90)90099-N.
- Bradski, G. (no date) 'The OpenCV Library', *Dr Dobb's j.Software Tools*, pp. 120–125.
- Breunig, M. M. *et al.* (2000) 'LOF: Identifying Density-Based Local Outliers', in *Proceedings of the 2000 ACM SIGMOD International Conference on Management of Data*, pp. 93–104.
- Briels, W, J. (1998) *Theory of polymer dynamics*. Online. Available at: <https://cbp.tnw.utwente.nl/PolymeerDictaat/index.html>.
- Bronshtein, I. *et al.* (2015a) 'Loss of lamin A function increases chromatin dynamics in the nuclear interior', *Nature Communications*. Nature Publishing Group, 6, pp. 1–9. doi: 10.1038/ncomms9044.
- Bronshtein, I. *et al.* (2015b) 'Loss of lamin A function increases chromatin dynamics in the nuclear interior', *Nature Communications*. Nature Publishing Group, 6, pp. 1–9. doi: 10.1038/ncomms9044.
- Bronstein, I. *et al.* (2009) 'Transient anomalous diffusion of telomeres in the nucleus of mammalian cells', *Physical Review Letters*, 103(1). doi: 10.1103/PhysRevLett.103.018102.
- Bui, M. *et al.* (2012) 'Cell-cycle-dependent structural transitions in the human CENP-A nucleosome in vivo', *Cell*, 150(2), pp. 317–326. doi: 10.1016/j.cell.2012.05.035.
- Cai, S. *et al.* (2018) 'Cryo-ET reveals the macromolecular reorganization of *S. pombe* mitotic chromosomes in vivo', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 115(43), pp. 10977–10982. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1720476115.
- Cho, S. *et al.* (2019) 'Mechanosensing by the Lamina Protects against Nuclear Rupture, DNA Damage, and Cell-Cycle Arrest', *Developmental Cell*. Elsevier Inc., 49(6), pp. 920-935.e5. doi:

10.1016/j.devcel.2019.04.020.

Chowdhary, S. *et al.* (2019) 'Heat Shock Factor 1 Drives Intergenic Association of Its Target Gene Loci upon Heat Shock', *Cell Reports*. Elsevier Company., 26(1), pp. 18-28.e5. doi: 10.1016/j.celrep.2018.12.034.

Chuang, C. H. *et al.* (2006) 'Long-Range Directional Movement of an Interphase Chromosome Site', *Current Biology*, 16(8), pp. 825–831. doi: 10.1016/j.cub.2006.03.059.

Cisse, I. I. *et al.* (2013) 'Real-Time Dynamics of RNA Polymerase II Clustering in Live Human Cells', *Science*, 245(August), pp. 664–667.

Darzynkiewicz, Z. *et al.* (1996) 'Cytometry of cyclin proteins', *Cytometry*, 25(1), pp. 1–13. doi: 10.1002/(SICI)1097-0320(19960901)25:1<1::AID-CYTO1>3.0.CO;2-N.

Dechat, T. *et al.* (2007) 'Alterations in mitosis and cell cycle progression caused by a mutant lamin A known to accelerate human aging', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 104(12), pp. 4955–4960. doi: 10.1073/pnas.0700854104.

Von Diezmann, A., Shechtman, Y. and Moerner, W. E. (2017) 'Three-Dimensional Localization of Single Molecules for Super-Resolution Imaging and Single-Particle Tracking', *Chemical Reviews*, pp. 7244–7275. doi: 10.1021/acs.chemrev.6b00629.

Eltsov, M. *et al.* (2008) 'Analysis of cryo-electron microscopy images does not support the existence of 30-nm chromatin fibers in mitotic chromosomes in situ', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 105(50), pp. 19732–19737. doi: 10.1073/pnas.0810057105.

Ester, M. *et al.* (1996) 'A Density-Based Algorithm for Discovering Clusters in Large Spatial Databases with Noise', in *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, Portland, OR, AAAI Press*. AAAI Press, pp. 226–231.

Fasciani, A. *et al.* (2020) 'MLL4-associated condensates counterbalance Polycomb-mediated nuclear mechanical stress in Kabuki syndrome', *Nature Genetics*. Springer US, 52(12), pp. 1397–1411. doi: 10.1038/s41588-020-00724-8.

Ferdman, B. *et al.* (2020) 'VIPR: vectorial implementation of phase retrieval for fast and accurate microscopic pixel-wise pupil estimation', *Optics Express*, 28(7), p. 10179. doi: 10.1364/OE.388248.

Furlong, E. E. M. and Levine, M. (2018) 'Developmental enhancers and chromosome topology', *Science*, 361(6409), pp. 1341–1345. doi: 10.1126/science.aau0320.

De Gennes, P. G. (1971) 'Reptation of a polymer chain in the presence of fixed obstacles', *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 55(2), pp. 572–579. doi: 10.1063/1.1675789.

Ghosh, S. and Zhou, Z. (2014) 'Genetics of aging, progeria and lamin disorders', *Current Opinion in Genetics and Development*. Elsevier Ltd, 26, pp. 41–46. doi: 10.1016/j.gde.2014.05.003.

Gibson, B. A. *et al.* (2019) 'Organization of Chromatin by Intrinsic and Regulated Phase Separation', *Cell*. Elsevier Inc., 179(2), pp. 470-484.e21. doi: 10.1016/j.cell.2019.08.037.

Grigoryan, A. *et al.* (2018) 'LaminA/C regulates epigenetic and chromatin architecture changes upon

- aging of hematopoietic stem cells', *Genome Biology*. *Genome Biology*, 19(1), pp. 1–21. doi: 10.1186/s13059-018-1557-3.
- Hahn, A. T., Jones, J. T. and Meyer, T. (2009) 'Quantitative analysis of cell cycle phase durations and PC12 differentiation using fluorescent biosensors', *Cell Cycle*, 8(7), pp. 1044–1052. doi: 10.4161/cc.8.7.8042.
- Hara, K. *et al.* (2012) 'NIH3T3 cells overexpressing CD98 heavy chain resist early G1 arrest and apoptosis induced by serum starvation', *Cancer Science*, 103(8), pp. 1460–1466. doi: 10.1111/j.1349-7006.2012.02304.x.
- Hinz, M. *et al.* (1999) 'NF- κ B Function in Growth Control: Regulation of Cyclin D1 Expression and G0/G1-to-S-Phase Transition', *Molecular and Cellular Biology*, 19(4), pp. 2690–2698. doi: 10.1128/mcb.19.4.2690.
- Hsieh, T. H. S. *et al.* (2015) 'Mapping Nucleosome Resolution Chromosome Folding in Yeast by Micro-C', *Cell*. Elsevier Inc., 162(1), pp. 108–119. doi: 10.1016/j.cell.2015.05.048.
- Humphrey, T. and Brooks, G. (2005) *Methods in molecular biology - cell cycle control*, Humana press. Edited by J. M. Walker. Totowa, New Jersey 07512: Humana Press.
- Johnson, B. R. *et al.* (2004) 'A-type lamins regulate retinoblastoma protein function by promoting subnuclear localization and preventing proteasomal degradation', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 101(26), pp. 9677–9682. doi: 10.1073/pnas.0403250101.
- Karoutas, A. and Akhtar, A. (2021) 'Functional mechanisms and abnormalities of the nuclear lamina', *Nature Cell Biology*. Springer US, 23(2), pp. 116–126. doi: 10.1038/s41556-020-00630-5.
- Kepten, E. *et al.* (2015) 'Guidelines for the fitting of anomalous diffusion mean square displacement graphs from single particle tracking experiments', *PLoS ONE*, 10(2), pp. 1–10. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0117722.
- Kepten, E., Bronshtein, I. and Garini, Y. (2013) 'Improved estimation of anomalous diffusion exponents in single-particle tracking experiments', *Physical Review E - Statistical, Nonlinear, and Soft Matter Physics*, 87(5), pp. 1–10. doi: 10.1103/PhysRevE.87.052713.
- Kim, J. and Kingston, R. E. (2020) 'The CBX family of proteins in transcriptional repression and memory', *Journal of Biosciences*. Springer India, 45(1), pp. 1–8. doi: 10.1007/s12038-019-9972-5.
- Lanni, J. S. and Jacks, T. (1998) 'Characterization of the p53-Dependent Postmitotic Checkpoint following Spindle Disruption', *Molecular and Cellular Biology*, 18(2), pp. 1055–1064. doi: 10.1128/MCB.18.2.1055.
- Lee, Y. C. G. *et al.* (2020) 'Pericentromeric heterochromatin is hierarchically organized and spatially contacts H3K9me2 islands in euchromatin', *PLoS Genetics*, 16(3), pp. 1–27. doi: 10.1371/journal.pgen.1008673.
- Levi, V. *et al.* (2005) 'Chromatin dynamics in interphase cells revealed by tracking in a two-photon excitation microscope', *Biophysical Journal*. Elsevier, 89(6), pp. 4275–4285. doi: 10.1529/biophysj.105.066670.

- Lieberman-Aiden, E. and Berkum, N. van (2009) 'Comprehensive mapping of long range interactions reveals folding principles of the human genome', *Science*, 326(5950), pp. 289–293. doi: 10.1126/science.1181369.Comprehensive.
- Lin, X. *et al.* (2021) 'Multiscale modeling of genome organization with maximum entropy optimization', *Journal of Chemical Physics*. AIP Publishing, LLC, 155(1). doi: 10.1063/5.0044150.
- Liu, N. Q. *et al.* (2021) 'WAPL maintains a cohesin loading cycle to preserve cell-type-specific distal gene regulation', *Nature Genetics*, 53(1), pp. 100–109. doi: 10.1038/s41588-020-00744-4.
- Lowe, D. G. (1999) 'Object recognition from local scale-invariant features', *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision*, 2, pp. 1150–1157. doi: 10.1109/iccv.1999.790410.
- Ma, H. *et al.* (2019) 'Cell cycle– and genomic distance–dependent dynamics of a discrete chromosomal region', *Journal of Cell Biology*, 218(5), pp. 1467–1477. doi: 10.1083/jcb.201807162.
- Maeshima, K. *et al.* (2020) 'Fluid-like chromatin: Toward understanding the real chromatin organization present in the cell', *Current Opinion in Cell Biology*. Elsevier Ltd, 64, pp. 77–89. doi: 10.1016/j.ceb.2020.02.016.
- Michalet, X. and Berglund, A. J. (2012) 'Optimal diffusion coefficient estimation in single-particle tracking', *Physical Review E - Statistical, Nonlinear, and Soft Matter Physics*, 85(6), pp. 1–14. doi: 10.1103/PhysRevE.85.061916.
- Nagano, T. *et al.* (2017) 'Cell-cycle dynamics of chromosomal organization at single-cell resolution', *Nature*. Nature Publishing Group, 547(7661), pp. 61–67. doi: 10.1038/nature23001.
- Narendra, V. *et al.* (2015) 'CTCF establishes discrete functional chromatin domains at the Hox clusters during differentiation', *Science*, 347(6225), pp. 1017–1021. doi: 10.1126/science.1262088.
- Nehme, E. *et al.* (2020) 'DeepSTORM3D: dense 3D localization microscopy and PSF design by deep learning', *Nature Methods*. Springer US, 17(7), pp. 734–740. doi: 10.1038/s41592-020-0853-5.
- Nishino, Y. *et al.* (2012) 'Human mitotic chromosomes consist predominantly of irregularly folded nucleosome fibres without a 30-nm chromatin structure', *EMBO Journal*. Nature Publishing Group, 31(7), pp. 1644–1653. doi: 10.1038/emboj.2012.35.
- Nitta, R. T. *et al.* (2006) 'Stabilization of the Retinoblastoma Protein by A-Type Nuclear Lamins Is Required for INK4A-Mediated Cell Cycle Arrest', *Molecular and Cellular Biology*, 26(14), pp. 5360–5372. doi: 10.1128/mcb.02464-05.
- Nitta, R. T., Smith, C. L. and Kennedy, B. K. (2007) 'Evidence that proteasome-dependent degradation of the retinoblastoma protein in cells lacking A-type lamins occurs independently of gankyrin and MDM2', *PLoS ONE*, 2(9). doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0000963.
- Nozaki, T. *et al.* (2017) 'Dynamic Organization of Chromatin Domains Revealed by Super-Resolution Live-Cell Imaging', *Molecular Cell*. Elsevier Inc., 67(2), pp. 282–293.e7. doi: 10.1016/j.molcel.2017.06.018.
- Ohno, M. *et al.* (2019) 'Sub-nucleosomal Genome Structure Reveals Distinct Nucleosome Folding Motifs', *Cell*. Elsevier Inc., 176(3), pp. 520–534.e25. doi: 10.1016/j.cell.2018.12.014.

- Oshima, J. *et al.* (2007) 'Accelerated telomere shortening and replicative senescence in human fibroblasts overexpressing mutant and wild-type lamin A', *Experimental Cell Research*, 314(1), pp. 82–91. doi: 10.1016/j.yexcr.2007.08.004.
- Pagano, M. (1996) *Cell Cycle — Materials and Methods*, *springer*. Edited by M. Pagano. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg. doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-57783-3.
- Pavani, S. R. P. *et al.* (2009) 'Three-dimensional, single-molecule fluorescence imaging beyond the diffraction limit by using a double-helix point spread function', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 106(9), pp. 2995–2999. doi: 10.1073/pnas.0900245106.
- Peddibhotla, S. *et al.* (2009) 'The DNA-damage effector checkpoint kinase 1 is essential for chromosome segregation and cytokinesis', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 106(13), pp. 5159–5164. doi: 10.1073/pnas.0806671106.
- Pedregosa, F. *et al.* (2011) 'Scikit-learn: Machine Learning in {P}ython', *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 12, pp. 2825–2830.
- Ricci, M. A. *et al.* (2015) 'Chromatin fibers are formed by heterogeneous groups of nucleosomes in vivo', *Cell*, 160(6), pp. 1145–1158. doi: 10.1016/j.cell.2015.01.054.
- Sanborn, A. L. *et al.* (2015) 'Chromatin extrusion explains key features of loop and domain formation in wild-type and engineered genomes', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 112(47), pp. E6456–E6465. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1518552112.
- Sanulli, S. *et al.* (2019) 'HP1 reshapes nucleosome core to promote phase separation of heterochromatin', *Nature*. Springer US, 575(7782), pp. 390–394. doi: 10.1038/s41586-019-1669-2.
- Scaffidi, P. . T. M. (2006) 'Lamin A-Dependent Nuclear Defects in Human Aging', *Science*, 312(5776), pp. 1059–1063. doi: 10.1126/science.1127168.
- Shaban, H. A. *et al.* (2020) 'Hi-D: Nanoscale mapping of nuclear dynamics in single living cells', *Genome Biology*. Genome Biology, 21(1), pp. 1–21. doi: 10.1186/s13059-020-02002-6.
- Shachar, S. *et al.* (2015) 'Identification of Gene Positioning Factors Using High-Throughput Imaging Mapping', *Cell*. Elsevier Inc., 162(4), pp. 911–923. doi: 10.1016/j.cell.2015.07.035.
- Shechtman, Y. *et al.* (2015) 'Precise Three-Dimensional Scan-Free Multiple-Particle Tracking over Large Axial Ranges with Tetrapod Point Spread Functions', *Nano Letters*. American Chemical Society, 15(6), pp. 4194–4199. doi: 10.1021/acs.nanolett.5b01396.
- Shechtman, Y. *et al.* (2017) 'Observation of live chromatin dynamics in cells via 3D localization microscopy using Tetrapod point spread functions', *Biomedical Optics Express*, 8(12), p. 5735. doi: 10.1364/BOE.8.005735.
- Da Silva-álvarez, S. and Collado, M. (2018) *Cellular Quiescence, Encyclopedia of Cell Biology*. Edited by H. D. Lacorazza. New York, NY: Springer New York (Methods in Molecular Biology). doi: 10.1007/978-1-4939-7371-2.
- Strom, A. R. *et al.* (2017) 'Phase separation drives heterochromatin domain formation', *Nature*,

547(7662), pp. 241–245. doi: 10.1038/nature22989.

Vivante, A. *et al.* (2019) 'Chromatin dynamics governed by a set of nuclear structural proteins', *Genes Chromosomes and Cancer*, 58(7), pp. 437–451. doi: 10.1002/gcc.22719.

Walter, J. *et al.* (2003) 'Chromosome order in HeLa cells changes during mitosis and early G1, but is stably maintained during subsequent interphase stages', *Journal of Cell Biology*, 160(5), pp. 685–697. doi: 10.1083/jcb.200211103.

Weiss, L. E., Naor, T. and Shechtman, Y. (2018) 'Observing DNA in live cells', *Biochemical Society Transactions*, 46(3), pp. 729–740. doi: 10.1042/BST20170301.

Deep subdiffusion ($\alpha = 0.1$)

Subdiffusion ($\alpha = 0.4$)

Free subdiffusion ($\alpha = 0.7$)

Super-diffusion ($\alpha = 1.4$)

MEF 3T3

MEF LmnaKO

MSD
color code

A

MEF 3T3

B

MEF LmnaKO

